
When war and famine hit home: A PhD student who stepped up

What would you do if war and famine broke out in your homeland—while you were ten thousand kilometers away, working on your PhD? This is what Hagos Mohammedseid Juhar faced. And this is how he chose to act.

Hello Hagos. Can you introduce yourself?

My name is Hagos Mohammedseid Juhar. I am from [Tigray, Ethiopia](#), where limited resources and financial hardship shaped my early life and fuelled my determination to pursue education against the odds. Despite being one of the top students in 10th grade, I chose to pursue a practical diploma in Plant Sciences over a traditional university path and contributed to agricultural development as a Development Agent, introducing innovations that gained national attention.

During my 2004 diploma graduation ceremony (3-years after 10th grade), I demonstrated the use of drip irrigation to the President of Tigray and regional delegates—showcasing practical solutions for sustainable agriculture in Tigray. Source of this and all photos: Hagos Mohammedseid Juhar.

My passion for plant sciences led me to earn a B.Sc. from [Mekelle University](#), where I excelled academically, joined the faculty, and built academic collaborations. I later advanced my studies with an M.Sc. in Plant Biotechnology from Wageningen University, The Netherlands and a postgraduate diploma in Biosafety from Ghent University, Belgium

focusing on sustainable and responsible use of biotechnology. I am currently a Ph.D. candidate at Academia Sinica in Taiwan, I explore the genetic factors affecting *Agrobacterium*-mediated transformation, driven by a commitment to improve crop transformation systems for contributing to global food security in the future.

2005: This is during my time as a Development Agent in Plant Sciences in rural Tigray—specifically in Begasheka, Kola Tembien, a region that later became one of the most strategic locations for Tigrayan forces during the war. Here in discussion with farmers about a project where Professor Emiru Birhane Hizikias (2024 African Academy of Sciences Fellow) from Mekelle University and others were involved,

2005: This is also during my time as a Development Agent in Plant Sciences in rural Tigray. (Left) My motor bike for transportation, (Right) An amazing Ficus tree where I often sit to read and listen to the radio, imagining my future life in a clean and beautiful environment.

I understand you left your family behind. Can you tell us more about that experience?

Since the start of the [Tigray war](#) on November 3, 2020, I hadn't been able to reach my family (my wife with two kids) for more than 40 days, and although I pushed hard to focus on my research, I could no longer concentrate. Imagine hearing that your wife and two young children—just 4 years and 7 months old—fled to the [AbiAdi mountains \(Kola tembien\)](#) to escape the bombing in Mekelle, only for AbiAdi itself to come under heavy attack.

I decided to return to Ethiopia during the war in January 2021 out of a deep sense of responsibility, identity, and solidarity with my family and people. Watching their suffering from afar was unbearable, and despite the risks, I felt morally compelled to stand with them—not just as a scientist or academic, but as someone rooted in their struggle and humanity. I knew that my name, Hagos, is uniquely tied to the Tigray region—easily recognizable, and in such a context, dangerously identifiable—yet I chose to go anyway, fully aware that I could be targeted. My return was not about politics or recognition, but about a profound commitment to justice and service. It meant reaffirming who I am—someone who stands with family and people in crisis, to help, witness, and uphold dignity. That decision remains one of the most defining acts of courage and conscience in my life—and in going back, I truly felt alive.

During this time of pain and struggle, I will always remember the unwavering support of my PhD advisor, Dr. [Erh-Min Lai](#), and the entire Plant and Environmental Microbiology (PEM) group at [IPMB, Academia Sinica, Taiwan](#). Dr. Lai helped extend my scholarship each semester during my two-year absence. Coincidentally, the peace agreement was signed just as the scholarship reached its limit. I consider myself incredibly fortunate—to have survived the war, supported my community, protected my family, and preserved my PhD scholarship.

What happened in Tigray in 2020, and how did the conflict impact access to food?

In November 2020, [a brutal conflict erupted in Tigray](#), involving Ethiopian, Eritrean, and regional forces against the Tigray People's Liberation Front (TPLF), leading to mass displacement and destruction. The war in Tigray devastated agriculture and food systems, leaving over 5.2 million people—more than 85% of the population—in urgent need of food aid (Annys et al. 2021). Before the conflict, the region had made meaningful progress in sustainable agriculture, but the war reversed these gains, with over 80% of farming households affected by looting, crop destruction, and loss of essential inputs (Fetien Abay and Biadgilgn Demissie 2022). Agricultural output dropped to as low as 15–25% of normal levels, and many farmers were left without seeds, oxen, or fertilizers for the next season. With humanitarian access blocked, supplies looted, and starvation used as a weapon of war, Tigray faced a man-made famine and the threat of long-term agricultural collapse without urgent global intervention.

A pre-war success story: The Farmers' Breeding Partnership, led by Professor Fetien and her team, empowered local farmers and significantly enhanced agricultural productivity (Adapted from Fetien Abay and Biadgilgn Demissie 2022). Professor Fetien Abay Abera is former interim president and professor of crop science at Mekelle University (my colleague). She is the 2014 East African Regional Laureate of [African Union Kwame Nkrumah Award for Scientific Excellence](#). She was also recognized among the top five African women scientists for her work in plant breeding in the African Women Professionals in Science Competition in 2009 and AWARD Fellow (African Women in Agricultural Research and Development) in 2010.

How did you and other scientists step in to respond to the food crisis?

Before the initiative began, I was witnessing heart-breaking scenes—people fainting in the streets and many dying simply because they had not eaten for days. News reports and TV coverage revealed that, amid widespread famine and starvation in Ethiopia's blockaded Tigray region, desperate people have been forced to survive by eating leaves and other wild plants (Anna 2021).

I kept asking myself: *What is my profession worth if my people are starving while I have knowledge, skills, and experience in agriculture and food systems?* Motivated by this, I began reaching out to key leaders in the agriculture sector—traveling by bicycle to meet them, including the former Ethiopian Minister of Agriculture (Dr. Eyasu Abraha) who was residing in Tigray at the time—despite almost a total collapse of services: no fuel, no banks, no electricity, no phone, no food, and no water. Fortunately, the Office of Science and Technology launched an initiative to mobilize researchers from all universities, research institutes and other sectors aiming to solve urgent societal problems under the siege. I joined the effort with a focus on agriculture, food, and nutrition, and we voluntarily gathered to form what became the Kirbit (team) for Agriculture, Food, and Nutrition Security under the Science and Technology (S&T) platform.

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In our first meeting, we introduced ourselves and shared project ideas that could directly address the crisis. We identified and documented over 17 projects, asked members to detail each one, and prioritized those that were realistic given our resources and expertise. To support implementation, we categorized the projects into six sub-teams, we secured land,

greenhouses, equipment, and seeds from institutions like Mekelle University, Tigray Agricultural Research Institute (TARI), Tigray Biotechnology Centre (TBC), Agricultural Transformation Agency (ATA), and others. We also created a network among members based on expertise and interest to strengthen collaboration. With the foundations in place, we were actively implementing many of these prioritized projects to fight hunger and rebuild food security in Tigray.

My background and outstanding team members enabled me to guide project identification, prioritize based on feasibility and local capacity, and connect with institutions to secure land, seeds, tools, and working spaces. It also helped in building trust among stakeholders and aligning efforts toward results.

You promoted the message “Eat more vegetables.” This may seem surprising to some readers. Can you explain why this was important?

Seeing people eat unknown wild leaves, I wore a T-shirt saying “Eat More Vegetables” (多吃蔬菜) as a bold symbol to inspire hope during the crisis. I received the shirt from the World Vegetable Centre in Taiwan and tried to secure vegetable seeds through UN contacts, but the blockade stopped our efforts. Instead, we taught communities to grow vegetables at home using local materials and created an offline app with step-by-step guidance in the local language. My message was clear: “We sleep amidst wealth, yet go hungry—so unjust that some survive by eating random leaves.”

This photo features a mobile application (local language: Tigrinya) designed by talented volunteer Efreem Gebremichael supported by Dr. Dawit Gebregziabher from Mekelle University to guide beginners step-by-step in practicing urban agriculture, including vegetable and fruit cultivation, mushroom production, small-scale animal farming, and organic soil preparation—both at home and in the community. Our slogan: ‘Our food from our home!’

Is there a specific positive anecdote or success story from that time that stands out to you?

—**The Seeds That Changed Everything: A Story of Courage, Community, and Cultivation**—At first, implementing our prioritized projects was extremely difficult due to the absence of technical experts in key offices and a general lack of confidence from

everyone in our vision. But we didn't give up—we began demonstrating homegrown food items in public spaces, and slowly, we started gaining the trust of local leaders and communities. **The turning point came when I discovered that vegetable seeds were available in the FAO store in Mekelle.** I shared my journey from Taiwan and the mission behind it, which moved the storekeeper to release the seeds without official approval—giving us the breakthrough we needed. When officials asked for their return, I urged them instead to mobilize urban farmers. Their swift action drew in more stakeholders, turning our efforts into a growing movement of hope and self-reliance. We promoted vegetable cultivation, explored edible wild plants, and launched a weekly TV program to inspire communities—transforming cities into green, food-producing spaces.

In the streets of Mekelle, answering questions and explaining to researchers from Mekelle University, local residents, and curious passers-by how to identify, grow, and prepare edible plants.

—My Crazy Proposal—and the Story of an Unexpected Victory—In a moment of urgency, I stood up in the meeting hall at Mekelle University and made what many might have called a crazy proposal: *“Let’s use every available piece of land for food production—regardless of who owns it—until this crisis is over.”* To my surprise, the idea didn't just resonate—it gained momentum. Within days, the government publicly endorsed the initiative, calling on citizens to support food production wherever possible. I was both stunned and deeply encouraged. That unexpected support became a turning point, giving us the momentum to dream bigger—and act faster.

At one of our weekly meetings at the Agricultural Transformation Agency (ATA) office, where volunteers shared innovative, rapid-impact ideas to help turn local resources into food and address the ongoing crisis.

—**Another Story of Hope: Saving 2,500 Chickens in Mekelle**—One urgent case came from Luul, a poultry farmer in Mekelle, whose 2,500 chickens were at risk due to a lack of feed. With quick coordination—especially help from Dr. Eyasu at TARI—we connected with Feed the Future and delivered the feed just in time. The chickens were saved, the farm survived, and a family’s livelihood was protected. A small but vital victory.

What were the key impacts of team-led interventions on agriculture, food prices, and nutrition in Tigray during the siege?

 Distributed vegetable seeds: 150 kg of onion and 12 kg of tomato seeds (worth 110,400 ETB) were distributed to farmers around Mekelle to kick-start local food production and stabilize the market.

 Urban agriculture scaled up: Over **1.2 million seedlings** were produced and distributed for home gardens; **purslane** was introduced to **4,000+ households** and planted at **TBC greenhouses**; **13,000+ vegetable seedlings** were given to women survivors of gender-based violence outside Mekelle. This inspired cities across Tigray to boost food production, leading to about 10-fold drop in prices for key vegetables after the intervention.

 Capacity building: More than **1100 people**—including youth, agricultural experts, and civil servants—were trained in nutrition-sensitive agriculture, urban gardening, and community-based food systems.

 Innovative, low-cost irrigation and inputs: Introduced **plastic bottle-based drip irrigation**, distributed **organic fertilizers, compost, and bio-pesticides** to households and farmers, improving productivity and sustainability.

 Community nutrition & emergency feeding: Supported the **Life Saving (LiSa) kitchen** that feeds **hundreds of children/family members daily**; led **nutrition education** and demonstrations of different foods across schools, hospitals, and communities.

What’s next for urban agriculture in Tigray?

Sadly, my early fears are becoming reality (Hagos et al. 2024): despite the peace agreement three years ago, food insecurity persists, worsened by the government abandoning the urban agriculture initiative for unknown political reasons after I returned to Taiwan. Many in Tigray continue to suffer hunger, which is why we refuse to step back. This summer, the Global Society of Tigrayan Scholars and Professionals (GSTS) will host a grand conference making food security a non-negotiable priority and a red line for all stakeholders. Sustaining urban agriculture in Tigray requires political will, institutional support, community investment, and a shared commitment to dignity, resilience, and self-reliance—a fight we are only beginning.

Finally, do you have a wish—for yourself, for your work, or for your country?

I wish for my PhD research to reveal impactful genetic factors affecting *Agrobacterium*-mediated transformation, while allowing me to strengthen my technical expertise and build meaningful collaborations with scientists and institutions around the world. I hope to contribute to solving food crises, especially in war-prone and vulnerable regions, where science and compassion can save millions of lives. For my Tigray region and my country Ethiopia, I dream of a future where innovation, peace, and resilience drive sustainable food systems—and where no one goes to bed hungry. This mission is deeply personal to me, and I will dedicate my life to turning it into reality.

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References and further reading

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[Academia Sinica, Taiwan, in March 2025.](#)

How I met Hagos

I met Hagos in April 2025 during a visit to Academia Sinica in Taiwan, where I had the chance to hear his inspiring story firsthand. I felt it would be most powerful to let him tell it in his own words.

Hagos and I share an academic connection, having both worked with [Francine Govers at Wageningen University](#). I only wish I could also claim his courage and dedication—qualities that he has channeled into helping his people and making a meaningful contribution to society.

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